
Public Policy and the Implementation Gap: An Analysis of the Consequences of NEP-2020

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ABSTRACT

The National Education Policy (NEP) 2020 was introduced as a transformative public policy initiative aimed at overhauling India's education system to make it more inclusive, multidisciplinary, and future-ready. While the policy proposes several progressive reforms—such as the Four-Year Undergraduate Programme (FYUGP), multidisciplinary education, the Academic Bank of Credits (ABC), and the integration of vocational training—its implementation at the grassroots level raises critical concerns. This micro-level study confines its scope to undergraduate colleges affiliated with the University of Burdwan, West Bengal, assessing the policy's real-world consequences through the lens of implementation gaps. Using a mixed-methods approach, the research draws on both quantitative and qualitative data collected from ten affiliated colleges (two urban and eight rural). Findings reveal that despite the ambitious restructuring, institutional preparedness remains weak. Colleges continue to face infrastructural constraints, faculty shortages, and administrative overload, leading to academic inconsistencies and limited student benefit. External dependencies, such as third-party vocational training providers, and excessive examination schedules further hinder the

intended goals of NEP 2020. This study highlights the widening gap between policy design and ground-level execution, emphasizing that successful education reform must be supported by adequate infrastructure, trained personnel, and coherent planning. The research concludes that bridging this implementation gap is essential for achieving the true spirit of NEP 2020, particularly in state-affiliated undergraduate institutions.

1. Introduction & Rationale

The National Education Policy (NEP) 2020, introduced by the Government of India, aims to bring transformational changes to the Indian education system (New Education Policy, 2020). However, the success of any public policy lies not only in its formulation but in its implementation at the grassroots level. This study seeks to evaluate the implementation status and consequences of NEP 2020, focusing specifically on undergraduate education in West Bengal, using the University of Burdwan and its affiliated colleges as a case study. As a researcher of Political Science, the work is situated at the intersection of public policy analysis and institutional governance, offering insights into the gap between policy intent and implementation reality.

2. Literature Review

The implementation of educational policy in India has long been subject to critical scrutiny, especially in relation to the systemic capacity to translate policy intent into institutional action. The National Education Policy (NEP) 2020, introduced after more than three decades, aims to overhaul the Indian education system by introducing structural changes, promoting multidisciplinary education, flexible curricula, and holistic development (MHRD, 2020). While the policy has been widely praised for its visionary goals, there is growing concern among scholars and practitioners regarding the practical challenges of its implementation. NEP 2020 outlines a series of transformative reforms including a four-year undergraduate program, the integration of vocational education, the establishment of multidisciplinary institutions, and the use of technology to promote learning (MHRD, 2020). The policy emphasizes equity, inclusion, and accessibility, yet scholars argue that these ambitious objectives face significant structural hurdles, especially in state-run and affiliated institutions (Tilak, 2019). Implementation theory, particularly as developed in the work of Pressman and Wildavsky (1973),

highlights how policies often fail not due to their design, but because of the absence of alignment among institutions, actors, and resources. In India, the decentralized governance structure adds complexity to implementation, as the state governments are responsible for the delivery of education while policy directives originate at the Union level (Chauhan & Jaiswal, 2025). Empirical studies have highlighted that colleges affiliated with state universities often suffer from weak infrastructural bases, inadequate funding, and bureaucratic rigidity, all of which affect their capacity to implement reforms like NEP (Banerjee, 2023). Furthermore, teacher training and orientation toward policy objectives remain inadequate, leading to implementation delays or distortions (Kumari, 2020). Specific studies focusing on West Bengal are still limited. However, initial reports indicate a slow and uneven rollout of NEP 2020 in the state, with institutions awaiting clear guidelines from affiliating universities (Bag & Chattopadhyay, 2024; Banerjee, 2023; Banerjee & Mete, 2025). From a public policy perspective, the implementation gap- the divergence between the goals set out in a policy and the outcomes actually achieved—remains a critical focus. Scholars argue that understanding this gap requires looking beyond administrative mechanisms to include political will, inter-governmental coordination, and institutional autonomy (Howlett & Ramesh, 1995; Sabatier & Mazmanian, 1980). NEP 2020, when viewed as a public policy case, offers fertile ground for exploring how macro-level policy interacts with micro-level institutional practices.

Research Gap

Despite the growing body of literature on NEP 2020, the following gaps remain:

1. Lack of micro-level institutional studies: Most existing works focus on the national or state-level analysis, with limited empirical insight from individual universities or affiliated colleges, especially in West Bengal.
2. Insufficient focus on policy-practice divergence: There is little exploration of the implementation gap as a public policy concern in the context of undergraduate colleges, which are often structurally under-resourced.
3. Neglect of political and governance perspectives: Few studies address how political factors, policy coordination, and governance structures influence the success or failure of NEP implementation.

4. Absence of consequence-based analysis: Much of the literature evaluates the potential of NEP 2020, but few explore the actual consequences—intended or unintended—resulting from partial or delayed implementation.

3. Objectives of the Study

1. To examine the awareness and preparedness of undergraduate colleges regarding NEP 2020.
2. To assess the extent of implementation of NEP 2020 at the UG level.
3. To analyze infrastructural, administrative, and pedagogical challenges in implementation.
4. To identify the policy gaps between NEP 2020 objectives and its on-ground execution.
5. To understand the institutional consequences (both intended and unintended) of NEP 2020.
6. To relate the findings to the broader discussion on public policy and governance in education.

4. Research Questions

1. How is NEP 2020 being understood and interpreted at the college level?
2. What steps have been taken by colleges affiliated with Burdwan University to implement the NEP 2020?
3. What infrastructural or administrative barriers hinder the implementation?
4. What are the observable consequences—positive or negative—of partial or full implementation?
5. How does the gap between policy and implementation reflect broader issues in educational governance?

5. Methodology

a. Study Area:

While the scope and intended consequences of NEP 2020 are broad and national in character, this study is deliberately delimited to undergraduate courses offered by colleges affiliated with the University of

Burdwan, West Bengal. This focused approach allows the researcher to conduct an in-depth micro-level analysis of policy implementation within a specific institutional and regional context.

b. Research Approach:

The study adopts a mixed-methods approach, combining both qualitative and quantitative techniques. This integrated strategy enables the researcher to gain a comprehensive understanding of the issue and to make empirically grounded and scientifically sound decisions based on both numerical data and contextual insights.

c. Sample Selection:

- **Sampling Method:** The study employs stratified random sampling, categorizing colleges based on key variables such as location (urban or rural). This ensures a more representative and balanced selection of affiliated undergraduate colleges under the University of Burdwan.
- **Sample Size:** The researcher selected a sample of 10 colleges affiliated with the University of Burdwan, comprising 2 from urban regions and 8 from rural regions. Data were collected from college principals, UG level faculty members, UG level students, administrative staff of these institutions using both quantitative (numerical) and qualitative methods to ensure a comprehensive understanding of the research problem.

6. Discussion

The **National Education Policy (NEP) 2020** introduces several transformative changes aimed at revamping the higher education system in India to meet the needs of the 21st century. At the undergraduate level, the policy proposes a flexible four-year degree programme with multiple entry and exit points, allowing students to receive a certificate, diploma, or degree depending on their duration of study. It emphasizes multidisciplinary education, enabling students to choose subjects across disciplines and promoting holistic development. The Academic Bank of Credits (ABC) system allows for credit accumulation and transfer across institutions, thereby increasing mobility and flexibility. The policy also seeks to strengthen the Choice-Based Credit System (CBCS) and integrate vocational education into all undergraduate programmes. Instruction in regional languages is encouraged, and teacher training is emphasized through continuous professional development. NEP 2020 calls for restructuring of institutions into autonomous, multidisciplinary colleges and universities, reducing institutional

fragmentation. Additionally, the policy advocates for the extensive use of technology in education delivery and assessment. These changes collectively aim to improve the quality, accessibility, and relevance of undergraduate education across the country.

While the changes proposed in NEP 2020 are progressive and much needed, especially in the context of global educational standards, their implementation has exposed significant structural limitations. One of the most pressing concerns is the **lack of corresponding improvements in the physical and institutional infrastructure** of higher education institutions, particularly at the undergraduate level. Colleges affiliated with state universities—such as those under the University of Burdwan—continue to operate with inadequate classrooms, limited laboratory and library resources, insufficient digital facilities, and a shortage of trained faculty. As a result, institutions have been **overburdened with new responsibilities** without being equipped to meet them effectively. Consequently, rather than improving academic outcomes, the hurried or partial implementation of NEP 2020 reforms has in some cases **worsened the academic environment**, leading to confusion, administrative overload, and a decline in teaching-learning quality. This highlights a critical **implementation gap** between policy vision and ground reality—underscoring the need to align policy goals with the actual capacity of institutions to deliver them.

One of the most significant structural changes introduced by NEP 2020 is the **Four-Year Undergraduate Programme (FYUGP)**, designed to offer students a broader, more research-oriented education that is in some cases considered equivalent to a postgraduate degree. This programme also includes multiple exit options and newly structured multidisciplinary courses. However, despite this academic expansion, **there has been no proportional increase in faculty strength**, nor any substantial improvement in the **training, capacity building, or pedagogical readiness** of existing faculty members. The number of teachers has largely remained the same, and many colleges—particularly in rural and semi-urban areas—lack qualified faculty to manage the diversified and intensive course load. As a consequence, instead of improving educational quality, the implementation of the FYUGP has led to **academic overload, inconsistency in curriculum delivery, and a dilution of learning outcomes**. This mismatch between policy ambition and institutional capacity exemplifies the broader **implementation gap** that undermines the success of NEP 2020 at the grassroots level.

The success of **multidisciplinary education**, as envisioned in NEP 2020, depends heavily on the availability of adequate institutional infrastructure—including sufficient classrooms, qualified faculty

across diverse disciplines, well-equipped laboratories, and relevant academic materials. However, in reality, most undergraduate colleges—particularly those affiliated with state universities like the University of Burdwan—continue to function with **the same limited infrastructure and faculty resources** as before the policy's implementation. No significant expansion has been made to support the broader curriculum and flexible subject combinations that NEP 2020 promotes. As a result, students often find themselves without proper academic support and are compelled to **depend heavily on private tuition or self-directed learning through the internet**. This situation not only defeats the core purpose of institutional multidisciplinary education but also **widens the gap between policy objectives and actual learning experiences**, further deepening inequality in access to quality education.

The **Academic Bank of Credits (ABC)** system, a key innovation under NEP 2020, is intended to promote academic flexibility by allowing students to accumulate, store, and transfer credits across institutions during their academic journey. While the concept is progressive and student-centric, in practice, **most institutions have not been adequately prepared to implement it**. Colleges affiliated with state universities, such as those under the University of Burdwan, **lack the necessary digital infrastructure, trained personnel, and regulatory clarity** required to operationalize the ABC system effectively. Additionally, there is limited awareness among faculty and students regarding how the system works, leading to confusion and underutilization. As a result, the intended benefits of mobility, flexibility, and lifelong learning have largely remained unrealized, highlighting once again disconnect between policy formulation and institutional preparedness.

One of the ambitious goals of **NEP 2020** is to integrate **vocational education** into undergraduate programmes to enhance the **employability** of students and bridge the gap between education and the job market. However, in practice, many affiliated colleges—particularly those under the University of Burdwan—**lack the basic infrastructure, equipment, and trained personnel** required to conduct these vocational courses effectively. To address this gap, institutions have been compelled to **depend on third-party providers such as Webel**, which merely supplies pre-recorded lecture videos and textual content. These resources are delivered without any **live interaction, practical engagement, or hands-on training**, either in physical classrooms or through online platforms. As a result, the vocational courses **fail to create meaningful impact or skill development** among students, falling far short of the policy's intended outcomes. This again reflects the larger issue of **implementation without institutional readiness**, undermining the transformative potential of NEP 2020.

NEP 2020 introduced a **semester-based Four-Year Undergraduate Programme (FYUGP)**, requiring students to complete **eight semesters** over the course of their degree. In the case of colleges affiliated with the University of Burdwan, each of these semester examinations is **centrally conducted and administered by the university**. As a result, a significant portion of the academic calendar is occupied with examination-related activities—such as preparation, conduction, evaluation, and result processing. This has led to a **disruption in the regular teaching-learning schedule**, leaving **little room for consistent classroom engagement or pedagogical continuity**. Faculty members often find themselves balancing administrative responsibilities related to examinations with academic duties, which affects both the quality and consistency of instruction. Consequently, the **emphasis on examinations has overshadowed meaningful academic interaction**, undermining the core objective of NEP 2020—to provide holistic and student-centric learning.

7. Conclusion

The National Education Policy (NEP) 2020 represents a landmark shift in India's higher education landscape, aiming to make the system more flexible, inclusive, and aligned with global standards. Its vision of multidisciplinary education, vocational training, academic credit mobility, and a four-year undergraduate structure reflects progressive thinking in public policy. However, the **ground-level realities in West Bengal, particularly in the affiliated colleges of the University of Burdwan**, reveal a substantial **implementation gap**. Despite the ambitious structural reforms, **no significant parallel investment has been made in institutional infrastructure, faculty development, or administrative capacity**. Colleges continue to function within outdated systems, struggling to meet the demands of the new framework without the necessary tools and resources.

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